

Human iNSCs (induced Neural Stem Cells) derived from human iPSCs (induced Pluripotent Stem Cells)

In vitro culture expansion and maintenance procedure

Frozen iPSC recorded in the file "Cells in dewar" (PhD – RISEUP > RISEUP ENEA experiments > iPSC > protocelli)

Growing Medium:

Stem diff progenitor medium (STEM CELL TECHNOLOGIES; CAT. #05833)*:

- Basal stem diff progenitor medium (48.5 mL)
- Supplement A (1 mL)
- Supplement B (50 µL)
- P/S (500 µL)

*Aliquot the stock separately (basal medium and supplements) and maintained at -20°C, to prepare fresh medium every time (50 mL final volume)!

Plate Coating:

*Aliquot the Geltrex 1:50 diluted in cold DMEM/F12 (on ice) and keep it at -20°C!

- Add 1 mL (Geltrex+F12)/well on P6 well plate and left at RT for 1h or keep in the fridge 4°C O/N**

**The plates can be coated in advance and kept at the fridge, sealed with paraffin, at least for a couple of weeks!

***Geltrex solution can be re-used at least 10 times (from one plate to the next one) when is maintain in the fridge!

Thawing of cells:

[They recommend thawing the cells at the end of day 0 and to replace the medium with fresh medium first thing in the next morning]

Day 0:

1. Do not thaw the cells until proper media and plasticware are on hand.
2. Remove the vial from liquid nitrogen and incubate in a 37°C water bath for the minimum required time until a small ice crystal remains. Maximum cell viability is dependent on the rapid thawing of frozen cells.
3. As soon as the cells are completely thawed, disinfect the outside of the vial with 70% ethanol.
4. In a laminar flow bio-safety II hood, collect the cells (around 1 mL) with a micropipette using blue pipet tip and transfer it to a sterile 15 mL conical tube, containing 3 mL of growing medium (see above for the recipe). *Warning: Be careful to not introduce any bubbles during the transfer process!*
5. Centrifuge at 0.3 rcf for 5 min and remove supernatant without touching the cell pellet.
6. Gently resuspend the cell pellet within the few µL of remaining medium after centrifugation by tapping (2-3 times) for a better disaggregation. Then, add 1 mL and quantified the viable cells (i.e., using Burker chamber).

7. Add, in each well of a P6 well plate (previously coated with Geltrex), 2 mL of growth medium + 10 μ M final concentration of Y-27632 (Cat. #72302; Stem Cell Technologies), a ROCK inhibitor (to reduce cell death after thawing). Then, seed **500K cells/well**.
8. **Warning:** *Immediately after thawing, we seed higher concentration of cells to reduce the % of cell death. Then, to maintain the cell on culture, we will reduce the concentration to **250K cells/well** in P6 well plate (or scaled it to other formats)!*

Day 1:

9. In the morning, change the medium to remove the ROCK inhibitor and potential floating death cells, adding fresh growth medium (w/o Y-27632).

From **Day 2:**

10. Maintain the NSC culture replacing the growth medium every 2-3 days, until reach ~80% confluency.

Warning: *It is important to maintain a certain confluency; too diluted will induced an accelerated senescence, too confluent will induce a transformation!*

For iNSC expansion:

- a. Remove the growth medium.
- b. Wash once with 1x PBS (tempered at 37°C).
- c. Add 0.5 mL of TrypLE 1x (Cat. 12604013; ThermoFisher) /well and leave in the incubator at 37°C (3-5 minutes), check under the microscope, and stop when cells get detached.
- d. Add 1 mL of growth medium/well and collect all the cell, transfer it in a 15 mL conic tube and centrifuge at 0.3 rcf for 5 min (RT).
- e. Gently resuspend the cell pellet within the few μ L of remaining medium after centrifugation by tapping (2-3 times), for a better disaggregation. Then, add 1 mL and quantified the viable cells (i.e., using a Burker chamber).
- f. Seed 250K cells/well (in a P6 well plate), previously coated with Geltrex + DMEM/F12

Freezing protocol:

- After treatment with TrypLE Express, count the cells and centrifuge at 300 rcf for 5 min
- Resuspend the cell pellet in Cryostore (CryoStor® CS10 Stem Cell Technologies) or, alternatively, use **90% FBS + 10% DMSO**
- *It is recommended to freeze at least 1 million/vial (in about 1 mL)!*

Representative Images of iNSC in culture:

**P5, 100% CONFLUENT,
24 H AFTER THAWING**

P6, 80% CONFLUENT, 24 H AFTER EXPANSION

